

Communication as a Strategy for Promoting the Execution of Community Development Projects in Rivers State.

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Abstract

This study examined communication as a strategy for promoting the execution of community development projects in Rivers State. Two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population of the study was 12,218 respondents which comprised of the entire community chiefs (618) and members of community based organizations (11,600) in Rivers State. The sample for this for this study was determined with the aid of Taro-Yamane formula which comprises of 103 community chiefs and 395 members of community based organizations. The instrument used in this study was a self developed questionnaire titled “Communication as a Strategy for Promoting the Execution of on Community Development Projects Questionnaire (ECSPECDPQ)”. The instrument was validated by the researcher’s supervisor, one expert in Community Development and one in Measurement and Evaluation from Rivers State University. The reliability of the instrument was established using the test re test method. Reliability Coefficients of 0.70 was obtained indicating the instrument was reliable. The research questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation statistics while the hypotheses were tested using z-test statistics at 0.05 significant level. The findings of the study revealed among others that provision of opportunities discourse among relevant stakeholders promote the execution of community development projects in Rivers State to a high extent. Based on the findings of the study it was recommended among others that Delebration and Discourse with important stakeholders should be examined explored widely in promoting the execution of significant community development. That way, these stakeholders will gain a chance to interchange key facts and opinions, that will quicken effectual service delivery in community development among engaged communities.

Keywords: Communication, Communication in Execution of projects and Community Development

INTRODUCTION

Most success in the execution of community development projects can be ascribed to effective communication. Effective communication takes place when the actual content and essence of information is successfully conveyed from one person (source) to another (receiver). According to Oyebamiji and Adekola (2008), through communication, members of the community can reach understanding of one another; build up trust in themselves; coordinate their actions and work out strategies for the achievement of set goals of the community. Batchelor (2010), further asserts that effective communication as a basis for promotion of good working relationships is very important for stimulating productive team working in the society. The implication of this is that communication provides an opportunity for people to engage in promotion of good relationships that stimulate group action which usually leads to productive community development initiatives that help to improve people’s living conditions. Good communication is very vital for the success of any community development project in various participating communities in human environment. Without which, it will be difficult to achieve good results in such human development initiatives to improve people’s living conditions in the society.

Communication is described as a veritable tool that enhances community cohesion and brings out good social working relationship. Okwor (2009) defines communication as a process and the activity of passing information from an individual to another person in the society. Fasel (2014) also defines communication as the ongoing interchange among people of thoughts, ideas, opinions, impressions, information and data by speech, writing or signs. Interestingly, communication is an ongoing interchange process which involves expression of thoughts, views, ideas, opinions, information and data in human environment in order to influence people’s action for an improved living condition in the society. Schramm (2011) states that communication is a transaction where the communicator and receiver are active and information is exchanged. Therefore, community development initiatives as a social development project requires effectual communication for effective service delivery in community development.

Community Development is not a new matter, but its existence is in line with human civilization (Community Development Exchange, 2013). However, Frank and Smith (2013) view community development as a process where community members come together to take collective action and generate solutions to common problems. It ranges from small initiatives within a small group to large initiative that involves the broader community. Community Development is defined as combined efforts of the community members, governmental, non governmental authorities and philanthropist in other to bring about positive or progressive change, growth in social, economical, cultural and problems of the community (Dokubo, 2015). According to Ezimah (2009), community development is seen as a process of special action in which the people of the community organize themselves for planning, define their own common/collective and individual needs and problems, make group or individual plans to meet their needs and resolve problems, execute their plans with maximum reliance on the community resources and materials from both governmental and the non-governmental agencies outside the community. Community development can also be defined as a movement signed to promote better living for the whole community with active participation, and if possible on the initiative of the whole community. This definition as a movement according to Onyeozu (2007) implies that community development always involves groups of peoples who share the same plight and beliefs and work together to achieve a particular aim that brings progress or socio-economic and political development in the community.

Communication in execution of community development projects is a group concern, where members of the engaging communities get to achieve their objective of improving people's living conditions in communities. Here, communication goes beyond interpersonal concerns to be more of a group concern in various communities in human environment which requires provision of opportunities for deliberation and discourse and provision of opportunities for sharing ideas to facilitate execution of community development process.

Provision of opportunities for discourse with pertinent stakeholders for community development is a key aspect of communication in community development process. Communication in dialogue and discussions is often times through word-of-mouth expressions for the interest of the target population. Okwor (2009) states that this indicates that ideas and opinions are exchanged among the participants in speech and in the course of discussion, new ideas and opinions emerge. The exposure of new suggestions and opinions in certain cases positively impact the views of target audience in the period of discussion. It is obvious that people in various participating communities cannot be engaged in dialogue and discussion with a view to facilitating the resolution of community development issues without communication between members of the participating communities, groups working to stimulate community development in the communities, corporate organizations' community development workers, members of the host communities of the concerned companies, funding agencies and field workers who work with project participants in various participating communities. Communication can be used in community development in dialogue and discussion session, especially during community consultations, community engagements and meetings to sensitize members of participating communities to understand the realities of the problems in their localities. Dialogue and discussion is guided by disposition of the audience in the meeting. Through the process of discussion, new ideas and opinions are highlighted in order to entrench the new ideas and opinions or sometimes to change views and attitudes in the meeting (Okwor, 2009). The development partners, corporate organizations and funding agencies engaged in community development process usually employ dialogue and discussions during community engagements as means of reaching the project participants at local community level to resolve issues which hinder community development in the concerned communities.

Also, provision of an opportunity for sharing ideas among people of various communities also is an important aspect of communication which people receive to facilitate people-oriented community development projects. Indeed, community development depends greatly on communication, especially in sharing relevant information and ideas necessary enough to enhance community development activities in the participating communities. Community development consists of a transaction between the community development practitioners or change agents and project participants in the participating communities. Peters in Garrison (2011) sees communication as a process of shared experience which is undertaken voluntarily. Communication provides people with opportunities to share information and experience relating to community development activities such as participatory rural appraisal (PRA), explanation of community development process; community needs identification and prioritization, community development planning, implementation, management and evaluation. To guarantee the sustainability of community development projects, the project participants must be adequately involved at all the stages of the projects beginning from project identification and conception to implementation. The sharing of information, ideas and experience among various communities encourage other communities to address similar situations in their localities (Imhabekhai, 2009). The

sharing of information, ideas, and experience is obviously part of human culture which must be used adequately to address prevailing similar problems in other social environment in the society.

Statement of the Problem

Effectual communication is key for the accomplishment of any community development project in various participating communities in human environment. Without which, it will be difficult to achieve good results in human development initiatives in other to improve people's living conditions in the society. Thus, no matter what kind of project - agriculture, infrastructures, fishery, water, governance, health - it is always valuable, and often essential, to establish deliberation among the concerned stakeholders. Unfortunately, most of the development projects in Rivers State are planned and implemented without effective communication approach, leading to failure of some of these projects. In 2009, lots of projects in Rivers state became "white elephants." These projects died a natural death because they were not being owned and sustained by the local population through communication and therefore could not survive beyond the exit of donors despite huge amounts of money spent on implementation of these projects. Although various strategies have over the years been proposed and implemented but these efforts have not yielded the desired result yet. Accordingly, there is need to properly establish dialogue among the concerned stakeholders for successful execution of community development projects. The question then is, could communication provide necessary knowledge that could promote the execution of community development projects in Rivers State? The answer to this question makes a study of this nature necessary.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate Communication as a strategy for promoting the execution of community development projects in Rivers State. Specifically, the objectives of this study are to:

1. Find out the extent to which provision of opportunities for discourse among relevant stakeholders promote the execution of community development projects in Rivers State.
2. Determine the extent to which provision of opportunities for sharing ideas among relevant stakeholders promote the execution of community development project in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. To what extent does provision of opportunities for discourse among relevant stake holders promote the execution of community development projects in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does provision of opportunities for sharing ideas among relevant stake holders promote execution of community development projects in Rivers State?

Hypotheses

In line with the objectivities of this study, the following formulated hypotheses were tested:

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of community-based organizations and community chiefs on the extent to which provision of opportunities for discourse among relevant stake holders promote the execution of community development projects in Rivers State.

Ho₂: There is no difference in the mean rating of community-based organizations and community chiefs on the extent to which provision of opportunities for sharing ideas among relevant stake holders promote the execution of community development projects in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the descriptive survey research design with a population of 12,218 respondents which comprises of the entire community chiefs (618) and members of community-based organizations (11,600) in Rivers State. The sample for this for this study was determined with the aid of Taro-Yamane formula which comprises of 103 community chiefs and 395 members of community-based organizations. The instrument used in this study was a self developed questionnaire titled "Communication as a Strategy for Promoting the Execution of Community Development Projects Questionnaire (CSPECDPQ)". The questionnaire was divided into two sections, A and B. Section A was used to gather demographic data of the respondents while section B was used to elicit responses from respondents on the questionnaire items drawn from the research questions of the study. The responses to the items in the questionnaire were structured on a four-point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). The instruments were dully validated by three experts. Two in Adult Education and one in Measurement and Evaluation, Rivers State University. The reliability of the instrument was established using the test re-test method. Copies of the instrument were administered to a sample size of 20 respondents

outside the study area and after a period of two weeks, the same questionnaire was administered to the same set of individuals. After which, the initial scores of the sample results was correlated using Pearson Moment Correlation (PPMC) which yielded a reliability index of 0.70, guaranteeing the reliability of the instrument. The data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation for answering the research questions raised for the study. Above 2.50 was considered high extent while below 2.50 was considered low extent. The null hypotheses were tested using Z-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT

Research Question 1: To what extent does provision of opportunities for discourse among relevant stakeholders promote the execution of community development projects in Rivers State?

Table 1: Mean Analyses on the extent to which provision of opportunities for discourse among relevant stakeholders promote the execution of community development projects.

S/N	Statement	CBOs N=395			Traditional Rulers N=103		
		Mean	S.D	Decision	Mean	S.D	Decision
1.	Through provision of opportunities for discourse, useful ideas are exchanged for community development.	3.29	0.71	High Extent	2.68	0.52	High Extent
2.	Relevant stakeholders get to really understand their prevailing realities.	2.68	0.52	High Extent	2.93	0.57	High Extent
3.	Through provision of opportunities for discourse, members of the community get to realize that they have the duty to initiate change.	3.52	0.92	High Extent	3.53	0.93	High Extent
4.	Relevant stakeholders get to resolve issues which hinder community development in their community.	3.20	0.69	High Extent	2.81	0.55	High Extent
Grand Mean		3.17	0.71	High Extent	2.99	0.64	High Extent

Analyzed data in Table 1 above on research question one, revealed that both respondents agreed that provision of opportunities for discourse among relevant stakeholders promote the execution of community development projects. With grand means of 3.17 and 2.99 for members of community based organizations and community chiefs respectively which are greater than the criterion mean of 2.50, the answer for research question one is that provision of opportunities for discourse among relevant stakeholders promotes the execution of community development projects to a high extent in several ways as listed above.

Research Question 2: To what extent does provision of opportunities for sharing ideas among relevant stakeholders promote execution of community development projects in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean Analyses on the extent to which provision of opportunities for sharing ideas among relevant stakeholders promote execution of community development projects.

S/N	Statement	CBOs N=395			Community Chiefs N=103		
		Mean	S.D	Decision	Mean	S.D	Decision
5.	Through provision of opportunities for sharing ideas, relevant stakeholders receive new ideas on how to facilitate people-oriented community development projects.	3.55	0.94	High Extent	3.47	0.88	High Extent
6.	Sustainable community development projects are guaranteed.	3.32	0.77	High Extent	2.93	0.57	High Extent
7.	Prevailing similar problems in other social environment are addressed	3.60	0.98	High Extent	3.64	0.99	High Extent
8.	Community members get to understand prioritization, planning, implementation, management and evaluation of development projects.	3.20	0.69	High Extent	3.28	0.74	High Extent
Grand Mean		3.41	0.85	High Extent	3.33	0.80	High Extent

Analyzed data in Table 1 above on research question one, revealed that both respondents agreed that provision of opportunities for sharing ideas among relevant stakeholders promote execution of community development projects. With grand means of 3.41 and 3.33 for members of community based organizations and community chiefs respectively which are greater than the criterion mean of 2.50, the answer for research question one is that provision of opportunities for sharing ideas among relevant stakeholders promotes execution of community development projects to a high extent in several ways as listed above.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean rating of community based organizations and community chiefs on the extent to which provision of opportunities for discourse among relevant stakeholders promote the execution of community development projects in Rivers State.

Table 3: Test of hypothesis one using Z-test Statistics

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	S.D	SL	DF	Z-cal	Z-tab.	Decision
CBOs	395	3.17	0.71	0.05	496	0.3	± 1.96	Accepted.
Community Chiefs	103	2.99	0.64					

Table 3 above shows that the z-calculated value of 0.3 is less than the z-table value of ± 1.96 for degree of freedom (496) at 0.05 significant level suggesting that there is no significant difference between the responses of community based organizations and community chiefs on the extent to which provision of opportunities for discourse among relevant stakeholders promote the execution of community development projects in Rivers State. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the mean rating of community based organization and community chiefs on the extent to which provision of opportunities for discourse among relevant stakeholders promote the execution of community development projects in Rivers State is accepted while the alternate is rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There is no difference in the mean rating of community based organizations and community chiefs on the extent to which provision of opportunities for sharing ideas among relevant stakeholders promote the execution of community development projects in Rivers State.

Table 4: Test of hypothesis two using Z-test Statistics

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	S.D	SL	DF	Z-cal	Z-tab.	Decision
CBOs	395	3.41	0.85	0.05	496	0.63	± 1.96	Accepted.
Community Chiefs	395	3.33	0.80					

Table 4 above shows that the z-calculated value of 0.6 is less than the z-table value of ± 1.96 for degree of freedom (496) at 0.05 significant level suggesting that there is no significant difference between the responses of community based organizations and community chiefs on the extent to which provision of opportunities for sharing ideas among relevant stakeholders promote the execution of community development projects in Rivers State. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference in the mean rating of community based organization and community chiefs on the extent to which provision of opportunities for sharing ideas among relevant stakeholders promotes the execution of community development projects in Rivers State is accepted while the alternate is rejected.

Discussion of findings

The result of the findings in research question one on provision of opportunities for discourse among relevant stakeholders to promote the execution of community development projects revealed that majority of the respondents agreed to a high extent that through provision of opportunities for discourse among relevant stakeholders, useful ideas are exchanged for community development, community members get to really understand their prevailing realities, and members of the community get to realize that they have the duty to initiate change and get to resolve issues which hinders community development in their community. This is in line with the opinion of Okwor (2009), who mentioned that through the process of discussion, new ideas and opinions are, indeed, highlighted in order to entrench the new ideas and opinions or sometimes to change views and attitudes in the meeting.

The result of the findings in research question two on provision of opportunities for sharing ideas among relevant stakeholders to promote the execution of community development projects revealed that majority of the respondents agreed to a high extent that through provision of opportunities for sharing ideas, relevant stakeholders receive new ideas on how to facilitate people-oriented community development projects, sustainable community development projects are guaranteed, prevailing similar problems in other social environment are addressed and community members get to understand prioritization, planning, implementation, management and evaluation of development projects. This is in line with the opinion of Peters in Garrison (2011), who sees communication as a process of shared experience which is undertaken voluntarily.

CONCLUSION

Based on the data analysis in the study, findings of the study and discussion made, it was concluded that communication as a strategy for promoting execution of community development in Rivers State include provision of opportunities for discourse among relevant stakeholders promote the execution of community development projects and provision of opportunities for sharing ideas among relevant stakeholders promote the execution of community development projects. The study further concluded that through provision of opportunities for discourse with relevant stakeholders, useful ideas are exchanged for community development, community members get to really understand their prevailing realities, and members of the community get to realize that they have the duty to initiate change and get to resolve issues which hinders community development in their community. Also through provision of opportunities for sharing ideas among relevant stakeholders, relevant stakeholders receive new ideas on how to facilitate people-oriented community development projects, sustainable community development projects are guaranteed, prevailing similar problems in other social environment are addressed and community members get to understand prioritization, planning, implementation, management and evaluation of development projects.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusion made, it was recommended that:

1. Delebration and Discourse with important stakeholders should be explored widely in promoting the execution of significant community development. That way, these stakeholders will gain a chance to interchange key facts and opinions, that will quicken effectual service delivery in community development among engaged communities.

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2. There should equally be constant communication with the different segments and community based organizations (CBOs) in the engaging communities which will stimulate collective action and participatory involvement of members of the engaging communities in promoting sustainable people-oriented community development projects.

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